

USING ENGLISH SONGS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' PRONUNCIATION

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ABSTRACT

Every good conversation starts with good listening. Actually, teaching English with grammar-translation method for a long-time results in Vietnamese students' deep knowledge of grammar, but a lack of English communication skills. One of the causes identified by Underwood (1989), Buck (2001, p.9), Osada (2004), Joseph Siegel (2011) is wrong pronunciation which leads to poor listening and speaking skill. Teaching pronunciation has not been properly focused on. It is often blamed on lack of time. Teachers need the method which can bring as many benefits as possible in limited time. Through the researchers' teaching practice, they find out that music can make incredible things in the classroom. The research question is: How can English songs performed by English speaking singers improve students' pronunciation?

The researcher uses three research methods: interview, observation and open-ended questionnaire to identify how wrong pronunciation obstructs listening and speaking of English as Foreign Language (EFL) students. Based on the analysis, the researcher introduces the innovation of using English songs performed by famous English-speaking singers as materials for teaching pronunciation to students in order to support and motivate non-major students.

Key words: pronunciation, English songs, music, listening skill

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this paper is using three research methods such as interview, observation and open-ended questionnaire to identify how pronunciation obstructs listening skill of English as Foreign Language (EFL) students based on which the writer introduces the innovation of using English songs performed by famous English-speaking singers as materials for teaching pronunciation to students in order to support and motivate non-major students in their listening skill.

In Vietnam, Russian had predominantly been taught before 1990. Other languages including English were only taught to a few learners who had particular objectives. However, the demand for learning foreign languages has completely changed since the political event in former Soviet Union. The number of EFL learners has rapidly grown in order to meet job requirements. Fluency in English becomes the first requirement for employees to show their work performance as well as to get promotion to in their workplace. Based on the real requirements of job market, universities and colleges has focused on communicative English.

And every good conversation starts with good listening. However, in Vietnam teaching English with grammar-translation method for a long time results in Vietnamese students' deep knowledge of grammar, but a lack of English communication skills, especially, listening skill. Namely, Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (or HUFVI for short), where I conducted research, most of the college freshmen (aged from 18-20) cannot complete half of the placement listening test at the beginning of first school year.

Several causes of poor listening have been identified by Underwood (1989), Buck (2001, p.9), Osada (2004), Joseph Siegel (2011), and one of them is wrong pronunciation as Jasone Cenoz & Ma Luisa Garcia Lecumber claimed. In Vietnam teaching pronunciation has not been properly focused on. It is often blamed on lack of time. Therefore, students' pronunciation should be improved. We, English teachers, have to find out the most effective method. We need the method which can supply as much practice as possible in limited time, because English is not non-major subject for students from other faculties.

And through my teaching practice I noticed that music can make incredible things in the classroom. I want to introduce using English songs presented by English speaking singer as material for teaching students pronunciation. My research question is:

How can English songs performed by English speaking singers improve students' pronunciation?

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Anderson and Lynch (1988) listening is really a receptive skill alongside with reading skills and the role of listener is no longer passive but active. This process involves listening to a speaker's accent and pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary and understanding the meaning of the word. Efficient listening is the process of not only every word but thoughts, feelings, and intentions. In brief, it is proved that listening comprehension is not merely the process of receiving of sound, but an interactive process.

Listening is the first language skill that children need to acquire. We spend far more time of our lives listening than speaking, reading or writing. Listening skill is a fundamental skill thanks to which we acquire a large amount of knowledge, information and perceive the world. New-born babies feel their mother's love and presence by listening to their soothing words, harmonious lullabies. Efficient listening skill is even more important than reading skill in contributing to academic success (Coakley & Wolvin, 1997; Truesdale, 1990). Therefore, an appropriate strategy for efficient teaching listening to non-major students is important to the success of language teaching and learning.

Underwood (1989) identified factors that affect effective listening comprehension. They are the speed of a native speaker, poor vocabulary, the signals of speaker, lack of knowing a context, concentration, tendency to listen to every word. According to Buck (2001, p.9) learners find listening difficult because it requires linguistic and non-linguistic sources in processing input. He also pointed out the differences between spoken and written language that Osada (2004) analyzed one by one in his article. For example, speakers usually pause, repeat, and use fillers to get

enough time for his arranging thoughts, they may use informal language such as slang, dialect and colloquialisms. Spoken language is often personal and highly expressive. Joseph Siegel (2011) also contended dilemmas for learners in listening. And I totally agree with the comments made by Jasone Cenoz & Ma Luisa Garcia Lecumberry (1999). They asserted that wrong pronunciation can lead to misunderstanding.

Phonetic differences in Vietnamese and English phonetic systems are the challenges for English pronunciation learning. Yet teaching pronunciation has not been focused properly at school. At the first lessons of English language learning, teachers often teach several phonetic rules cursorily, and then ask students to repeat some typical sounds. Teachers often pay more attention to segment such as vowels and consonants than to supra-segmental components such as stress, rhythm, intonation, assimilation, elision, liaison, without knowledge about which we cannot perceive connected speech. Practicing pronunciation should be conducted regularly throughout the learning process, not just at a few classes as directed in the curriculum.

Researchers and teachers find out singing English songs is the interesting way of improving students' pronunciation, because most of us love music. We cannot imagine our lives without music which pervades every aspect of our lives. Scientists encourage mothers to play music for their fetus. Especially, masterpieces enhance brain development. It is common to see teenagers with earphones humming a tune on buses, at stations, restaurants or coffee shops. It is assured that their music list is wide. Perhaps teachers want their list to contain their lessons or lectures instead of the songs they are humming. Why don't we use English their favorite songs to illustrate the phonetic rules?

There have been previous researches into using English songs to teach grammar, vocabulary for learners. Karen Kunkel Ready suggested teaching grammar through music, but I want to use English songs as materials for teaching pronunciation to students in order to support and motivate them in practicing pronunciation.

Educators acknowledged that education only achieves the best results when it is based on the needs and interests of the learner, which creates student-centered classes. In Carmen's opinion, music and language share some features. Both relate to processing sounds, convey a message, and include in themselves pitch, volume, prominence, stress, tone, rhythm, and pauses. We can learn both through exposure. Prosodic and melodic lessons electrify the learning because they are memorable and fascinating. Therefore, Marilyn Abbot (2002) asserted that music activities used in the language classroom have power to excite, move and soothe the learners and help them remember things. Smooth melodies, expressive lyrics easily go into the heart and stay there longer than any materials people have to keep in mind, which was called the "song stuck in my head" phenomenon by Murphy (1996). Repeating oral exercises is very boring and monotonous, whereas singing a favorite song is a pleasure. While listening to a pleasant song, we'll have the desire to be able to sing the song. Perhaps many Vietnamese can sing along with the song "Happy New Year" by ABBA band due to its great melody and its annual broadcast on television on New Year's Eve. Obviously, sounds, structures and pronunciation rules are naturally, unconsciously absorbed into their mind without any efforts. Jourdain (1997) believed that music makes us

become like drug addicts as we listen and listen again. Byrne (1984) confirmed that repeating passages is the best way to facilitate pronunciation and when authentic passages are used for teaching, the students' listening comprehension performance will be improved better.

In particular, English is the non-major subject for HUFU students from faculties except for English faculty . They hardly have opportunities to communicate with English native speakers. They even can't access the internet because there are no adequate facilities for learning. Consequently, I want to use English songs performed by English speaking singers as materials to support and motivate students to learn pronunciation. Students are always eager for songs at top of the world rankings often presented by the singers from countries where English is the first or second language. They are ready to sing the song again and again, They can memorize the song unexpectedly quickly. Both teachers and students feel relaxed and comfortable at the lesson. In addition music integrated lessons encourage student autonomy. After school they will learn more about the songs, the singers performing them, even their country and culture. Autonomy is extremely essential in a student-centered classroom with communicative approach.

3 DATA COLLECTION

3.1 Methodology

Qualitative methodology

I was conducting my research following qualitative methodology because Hinchey (2008) stated that the quantitative perspective claimed there is a unique truth existing independent of subjective human desire and being waited to be explored while the qualitative one argued that there are many various realities which depend on our senses and background that the knowledge human acquires is indeed the individual perception. During listening comprehension Vietnamese students face the different difficulties from other countries students' problems which may be caused by ethnic characteristics. It is easy for students speaking Romance languages (except for English) as the first language to get familiar with English aspects of connected speech such rhythm, assimilation, elision, liaison, as well as stress, intonation, strong and weak forms etc. which are challenging for Vietnamese students. Differences between Vietnamese and English phonetic systems interfere them in listening to authentic speech.

Qualitative methodology helps me have a deep look inside the issue and understand how my students viewed effects of English songs on their progresses in their listening skill. (Different Kinds of Qualitative data collection methods/ Maria Smith and Tamsin Bowers-Brown/112)

In order to collect data for my research, I used three following methods: semi-structured interview, open class observation and open-ended questionnaire the knowledge from which is subjective and it includes bias, a feature of qualitative research. (Lena Dahlberg and Colin McCaig, 2010). Yet it could provide deep insight into the issue.

3.2 Data collection

3.2.1 Semi-structured focus group interview

I employ semi-structured focus group interviews to learn students' knowledge of phonetic phenomena and its impacts on their listening comprehension, their attitude toward English songs and pronunciation classes accompanied by songs, effects of the kind of lesson on their listening skill. Using this method, I could encourage my shy students who rarely dared to express criticism of their teachers or their teaching methods to talk more freely about their wishes (Lena Dahlberg and Colin McCaig, 2010, p. 23) because of traditional rules in Vietnam. Hinchey (2008, p. 82) pointed out that strengths of semi-structured interview make them feel more confident and evokes "a kind of creative synergy".

The duration for conducting semi-structure interviews is a week. Each focus group interview is scheduled to last about 20 minutes. I randomly chose five students from each piloted class whose order in their class are 3, 8, 15, 21, and 46. The total number of interviewed groups was 3. Such a way of selection as Baker's (2011, pp. 269-273) stated could supply various data to the interviewer and give sample students more explanation if necessary (Lena Dahlberg and Colin McCaig, 2010, p. 119). All interview were recorded on audiotape and taken notes by the researcher.

3.2.2 Open class observation

Open class observation was chosen because of its popularity and effectiveness in school setting as Maria Smith and Tamsin Bowers-Brown stated in *Different kinds of qualitative data collection methods*/122. Using this method I could be involved in activities as a teacher and adjust materials or method of teaching.

During the process of research, I observed both student activities and attitude inside classroom and during the 15-minute break time after the innovated lesson and simultaneously ticked in the checklist. The checklist had 2 parts. The first section included information about the class, the title of introduced song, and the date of lesson. The second one was divided into such 3 column as contents I wanted to investigate, extents of frequency with 3 sub-columns (yes, somewhat, not at all), and the last was note and comment. All 5 innovated lessons in each sample class were observed. The total number of observed lessons was 15. Carrying out class oobservations for periods confirmed stability of student behavior and attitude in reaction to the innovation.

3.2.3 Open-ended questionnaire

An open-ended questionnaire which Hinchey (2008, p. 83) rated as the most effective method to collect large data for a short time was used to support the knowledge withdrawn from the methods above.

In order to determine students' interest and attitude toward to using English songs for learning English Roszainora Setia et al. (2012) used a questionnaire. O'Neill (2009) also used it to explore facets of pedagogy for English as a Foreign Language while Pangsapa (2006) employed this method to investigate how students evaluated benefits the learning phonetics to their listening and

speaking skills. The questionnaires were delivered to all students in the three sample classes. The questionnaire had to be completed within 15 minutes and given back to the researcher shortly thereafter. Discussion was not allowed in order to avoid identical questionnaires

3.3 Triangulation

Using three methods meets triangulation which helps a researcher decrease ambiguity and increase his/her confidence in the research findings. (Patricia H. Hinchey Action Research /76). The duration for data collection is limited and same size is small, so triangulation is required to ensure data validity as Lena Dahl 35 explained.

4 DATA ANALYSIS

All data collected by three methods were analyzed after being read many times, described with comments. While reading data, I identified the patterns which took shape in the behavior, relationship and emotion categories. The next step was coding the identified categories. After coding categories, it was easy to formulate key findings. The findings were Student attitude toward typical listening lessons, Student attitude toward listening lessons integrated with music, Effects of lesson with music on student behavior, Effects of lesson with music on student autonomy, Effects of lesson with music on student listening skill.

4.1 Focus group interview

Recording and video tapes from interviews are transcribed verbatim immediately at the of the interview day, which helped me to recall every detail of the interviews. After multiple reading, transcripts were described, coded and compared in order to withdraw findings.

4.2 Open class observation

All open class observation checklists and notes as well as comment were described and coded into categories, thanks to which the patterns emerged. Interesting stories, infrequent or unique event happening during observation were taken note of in order to illustrate the themes. Student reactions both inside and outside the classroom were grouped into “student attitudes towards innovated material”, “effects of songs on student listening skill”, “effects of songs on student autonomy”

4.3 Open-ended questionnaire

I used Excel Software spreadsheet to analyze the data from questionnaires which took me a week

5 CONCLUSION

The research has revealed the following important findings:

5.1 Student attitude toward traditional pronunciation lessons

when interviewed students thought that they did not help in their listening skills. They had no idea about such aspects of connected speech as rhythm, assimilation, elision or liaison which were obstructions in their listening to authentic speech.

5.2 Student attitude toward the innovated lessons

Students were excited in the lessons integrated with music. They wanted to show themselves by giving information about the song or the singer they had known before. The introduced song attracted students' attention till the end of class.

5.3 Effects of the lesson with music on student behavior

When the melody of the song was played, students listened to it attentively. They even swayed their body to the music. There was a closer cooperation between the teacher and the students

5.4 Effects of the lesson with music on student autonomy

Students talked about the songs both before and after learning them. They could share information or pictures they found on the Internet with the teacher.

5.5 Effects of the lesson with music on student listening skill

At the end of the innovation, approximately 77% of students said that it was easier for them to realized known words in authentic speech. They have become familiar with rhythm, linking, elision, assimilation, strong or weak forms etc.

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